

Investigating the Determinants and Variation of Laboratory Testing in Primary Care Using Real-World Data from Electronic Medical Records

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Levy Jäger
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First reviewer: Prof. Stefan Boes

Second reviewer: Prof. Oliver Senn

Co-Promoter: PD Dr. med. Stefan Markun

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SHORT SUMMARY

Laboratory testing plays an important role in primary care as a tool to inform decisions about the diagnosis and treatment of disease. Previous research has found a temporal increase and considerable variation in its use among Swiss general practitioners. While this suggests that laboratory testing is a potential target for efficiency improvement strategies, specific evidence on the use of the most common laboratory tests is lacking. In the three studies presented in this thesis, we therefore aimed to investigate the determinants and the variation in the use of laboratory tests frequently ordered in Swiss primary care: renal function tests, thyroid-stimulating hormone, and ferritin. We conducted three retrospective cohort studies using data from the FIRE project, a database of electronic medical records maintained by the Institute of Primary Care of the University of Zurich. We observed relevant gaps in the quality of renal function monitoring in patients with chronic kidney disease, an underuse of thyroid function monitoring in patients with potential hypothyroidism, and a large effect of the choice of ferritin cut-off on the diagnostic rate of iron deficiency. Our results can help to inform and assess future initiatives to improve the use of laboratory testing in Swiss primary care. In addition, our projects highlight the potential of the FIRE project to serve as a platform for research, quality monitoring, and policy impact evaluation.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ATC	Anatomic Therapeutic Chemical classification system
BMI	body mass index
CI	confidence interval
CKD	chronic kidney disease
EMR	electronic medical record
FHIR®	Fast Healthcare Interoperable Resources®
FIRE	Family medicine Research using Electronic medical records
GP	general practitioner
GTIN	Global Trade Item Number
HIA	Health Insurance Act
ICC	intraclass correlation coefficient
ICPC-2	International Classification of Primary Care, 2 nd edition
IQR	interquartile range
ITS	interrupted time series
KDIGO	Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes
HIBO	Health Insurance Benefits Ordinance
LOINC®	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes®
MEM	mixed-effects model
MHR	median hazard ratio
MOR	median odds ratio
PCG	pharmaceutical cost group
QI	quality indicator
RAAS	renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system
RECORD	REporting of studies Conducted using Observational Routinely-collected health Data
ROR	range odds ratio
RWD	real-world data
TSH	thyroid-stimulating hormone
UPC	usual provider of care

CHAPTER 1 Introduction

1.1 Background

1.1.1 The Role of Laboratory Testing in Primary Care

Laboratory testing is an essential component of medical decision making, providing objective evidence of a patient's health status.¹ Its importance is particularly evident in primary care, where general practitioners (GPs) request laboratory analyses to guide the diagnosis, treatment, and monitoring of disease.² On the other hand, the use of laboratory testing in primary care has recently been the subject of controversy due to increasing frequency,³ variation,⁴⁻⁶ and a high rate of unnecessary repeat testing.^{7,8} These observed patterns suggest a risk of overutilization, and indeed, a significant proportion of laboratory testing requests in primary care have been found to be inappropriate.^{2,9} The overuse of diagnostic testing, referred to as overtesting, can have a negative impact on health systems through two mechanisms: increased healthcare spending,¹⁰ which can represent a waste of resources, and patient harm due to overdiagnosis and subsequent overtreatment.¹¹ Nonetheless, it is important to note that variation in the use of laboratory testing in certain situations may also be a sign of underuse, which can also have adverse consequences through delayed or missed diagnoses and treatments.^{3,12}

1.1.2 Primary Care Services in Switzerland

In Switzerland, primary care is the first point of contact for the majority of the population for health-related questions.¹³ Primary care providers are typically physicians, roughly divided into those who predominantly care for children and adolescents and those who predominantly care for the adult population.¹⁴ In this thesis, we address the second group and refer to these physicians as GPs, who are typically board certified in general practice or in general internal medicine.

In Switzerland, health insurance is mandatory for all residents.¹⁵ Individuals pay premiums to an insurance company of their choice, along with annual deductibles and coinsurance fees for the health services they receive. According to the Federal Act on Health Insurance (Health Insurance Act, HIA*), a principle of trust applies and it is generally assumed that physicians provide services that meet the principle of effectiveness, appropriateness, and economic efficiency.¹⁶ Accordingly, compulsory health insurance is required to cover a wide range of diagnostic and therapeutic services in primary care. GPs are mostly paid on a fee-for-service basis according to a national tariff system for outpatient services that prohibits overbilling.¹⁵

While the Swiss population is largely satisfied with the quality of its healthcare system, especially with primary care services,¹³ concerns about low efficiency due to constantly rising costs have been the subject of much debate.¹⁵ In response, several initiatives have been launched to improve the quality and efficiency of the Swiss healthcare system, including primary care.¹⁷ An important recent development was an amendment to the HIA that came into effect in 2021, requiring Swiss physicians to implement quality development activities and to publish quality measures since April 2022.^{18,19}

1.1.3 Laboratory Testing in Swiss Primary Care

The laboratory tests that are covered by compulsory health insurance for ambulatory care are included in the Federal Analysis List, which is edited by the Swiss Federal Department of Home Affairs and published regularly as an appendix to the Health Insurance Benefits Ordinance (HIBO).^{20,21†} In addition, the Federal Analysis List specifies laboratory tests and their tariffs that GPs can bill for and perform as point-of-care tests using the facilities of their own practice.

* German: Bundesgesetz über die Krankenversicherung (Krankenversicherungsgesetz, KVG)

† German: Verordnung des Eidgenössischen Departements des Inneren über Leistungen in der obligatorischen Krankenpflegeversicherung (Krankenpflege-Leistungsverordnung, KLV)

The Federal Office of Public health monitors the development of costs arising from laboratory testing in Switzerland based on the analyses charged through the Federal Analysis List.²² In 2021, a total of 117.2 million laboratory tests were billed through the Federal Analysis List, generating revenues of 1.90 billion Swiss francs, or 5.24% of the gross health insurance benefits for that year.²³ Of this total, 508 million Swiss francs were charged for 46.8 million ambulatory point-of-care tests. The total revenue for analyses billed from the Federal Analysis List increased by 58.2% from 2010 to 2021, along with a 49.8% increase in testing volumes over the same period. While the direct costs of primary care laboratory testing are a seemingly small part of overall healthcare costs, the indirect costs generated by the resulting downstream diagnostic and therapeutic cascades can be substantial.²⁴

Despite these recent developments, there is currently little evidence to specifically support policies aimed at increasing the efficiency of the use of laboratory testing in Swiss ambulatory care. In this context, our research group at the Institute of Primary Care of the University of Zurich conducted a comprehensive analysis of the use of laboratory testing over the decade from 2009 to 2018 using data from primary care electronic medical records (EMRs).²⁵ This study provided the first panoramic view of laboratory testing frequencies by Swiss GPs. The average GP ordered laboratory testing in 20% of consultations, most commonly requesting complete blood count panels, C-reactive protein, and serum creatinine. Most of the most frequently requested laboratory tests showed sex- and age-adjusted temporal increases, consistent with previous results from a British study.³ Moreover, the study found substantial variation among GPs in the frequency of use of these laboratory tests, again reflecting findings from the international literature.⁴⁻⁶

Our previous results point to issues of potentially unwarranted variation and potential inefficiency in the use of laboratory testing in Swiss primary care. However, the evidence for interventions to improve the quality of laboratory testing in primary care is generally weak.^{26,27}

Therefore, there is a need for specific research to better understand the processes involved in the use of specific tests.

1.2 Aims

Motivated by our previous findings, we conducted the studies presented in this thesis as in-depth investigations of the use of specific laboratory tests in Swiss primary care. We focused on high-volume analyses because they represent a considerable portion of laboratory spending and the quality of their use potentially affects a large number of patients. Each study examines the use of laboratory testing for the diagnosis and management of a specific condition, focusing on determinants and clinical variation. The specific background and aims of the three studies are summarized below.

1.2.1 First Study: Renal Function Testing in Chronic Kidney Disease

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a common condition characterized by a progressive decline in renal function that, without treatment of the underlying cause, can eventually lead to end-stage renal disease requiring kidney transplantation or dialysis.²⁸ Common cardiovascular risk factors, such as diabetes or hypertension, are the most common cause of CKD in high-income countries.²⁹ Conversely, CKD represents an independent risk factor for cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.³⁰ According to the landmark 2012 guidelines of the Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) group³¹, the mainstay of its diagnosis and monitoring is renal function testing. Specifically, renal function testing involves measuring serum creatinine, a blood parameter that quantifies the kidney's filtering ability, and of urinary albumin, which quantifies the degree of kidney damage.

Early diagnosis and management of CKD are essential to prevent its progression and associated mortality.³² However, studies conducted in several countries have identified gaps in the

quality of care for CKD, particularly regarding the underuse of renal function tests for screening in high-risk patients with diabetes, hypertension, or cardiovascular disease.³³⁻³⁵ On the other hand, drugs in the sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor class, originally approved for diabetes, have recently been shown to effectively reduce the progression of CKD and the associated cardiovascular mortality,³⁶ and as a result their indication has been expanded to include CKD irrespectively of diabetes.³⁷ With the advent of this novel therapeutic option that can significantly improve the prognosis of CKD, ensuring high quality in the early detection and monitoring of CKD has become even more important.

While our previous analysis found that serum creatinine was widely ordered in Swiss primary care, evidence on the quality of its use in the context of CKD was lacking. Surprisingly, there were also few data on the general management of CKD in Switzerland. Therefore, the aim of this study was to obtain an overview of the quality of CKD care provided by Swiss GPs, focusing on care processes related to the use of renal function testing for early detection of CKD and for monitoring in patients with established CKD.

1.2.2 Second Study: Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone Testing in Hypothyroidism

Hypothyroidism is a common condition involving a failure of the thyroid gland to produce hormones that regulate the levels of metabolic activity.³⁸ Its biochemical hallmark is the presence of elevated blood levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) produced by the pituitary gland, and its first-line therapy consists of pharmacologic thyroid hormone replacement.³⁹ GPs may be prompted to request TSH testing in patients who present with symptoms of reduced metabolism that are associated with hypothyroidism, such as fatigue, weight gain, or cold intolerance.⁴⁰ Hypothyroidism becomes more prevalent with increasing age, and clinical guidelines are conflicting as to whether screening in the asymptomatic general population with routine TSH testing is warranted.⁴¹⁻⁴³ Not surprisingly, considerable variation in the use of TSH

testing for hypothyroidism screening has been noted,⁴⁴ with according concerns about overuse and, consequently, overtreatment with thyroid hormone replacement.^{45,46}

After a finding of elevated TSH levels, repeat TSH testing after several months is recommended to confirm a diagnosis of hypothyroidism.^{47,48} While previous studies have revealed inconsistencies in the general use of TSH for hypothyroidism screening and in thyroid hormone prescribing,^{45,46} the immediate consequences of elevated TSH levels in primary care had not been addressed. The aim of this study was therefore to investigate the course of action of GPs following the detection of a TSH elevation, in terms of whether they would use repeat TSH measurement to confirm hypothyroidism, as recommended, or whether they would rather opt for direct thyroid hormone replacement.

1.2.3 Third Study: Ferritin Testing in Iron Deficiency

Iron plays a critical role as a micronutrient in the formation of red blood cells, and reduced bodily iron stores can lead to a shortage of red blood cells called anemia.⁴⁹ Iron deficiency is the most common nutritional deficiency worldwide, and subsequent anemic iron deficiency is a leading cause of years lived with disability.⁵⁰ Non-anemic iron deficiency, a reduction in iron stores that does not yet lead to anemia, has emerged as a distinct clinical entity.⁵¹ Both anemic and non-anemic iron deficiency are often associated with non-specific symptoms, such as fatigue, weakness, or hair loss, and are diagnosed based on the presence of reduced blood levels of the iron-storing protein ferritin. However, the recommended cut-offs for the diagnosis of iron deficiency and the initiation of iron replacement therapy vary widely across guidelines.⁵² Before this study was conducted, there was no evidence on how the choice of different ferritin cut-offs affects the rates at which iron deficiency is diagnosed. This would particularly important to know in Switzerland, where it was estimated that 27% of the population received ferritin testing in 2018,⁵³ and the choice of cut-off potentially affects a large number of patients. The choice of

the ferritin cut-off also has important economic implications, as Swiss physicians often prefer the more expensive intravenous route of iron replacement to the less expensive oral option.⁵⁴ In this study, we therefore examined the potential impact of different ferritin cut-offs on the incidence of iron deficiency diagnoses in primary care. In addition, we aimed to investigate how GPs use ferritin testing in the first place, focusing on the role of clinical and demographic determinants.

1.3 Methods

1.3.1 Setting and Data Source

The studies presented were conducted as retrospective analyses using data from the Family medicine Research using Electronic medical records (FIRE) project hosted by the Institute of Primary Care of the University of Zurich.⁵⁵ Founded in 2009, the FIRE project is the oldest and largest database of EMRs from Swiss primary care.⁵⁶ Until 2021, the FIRE database contained standardized, structured data from the following EMR components:

- consultation dates;
- sex and year of birth;
- reasons for encounter coded according to the International Classification of Primary Care, 2nd edition⁵⁷ (ICPC-2);
- medication prescriptions (prescription dates and dose schemes) coded in the Anatomic Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification system,⁵⁸ representing the active principles, and as Global Trade Item Numbers (GTINs),⁵⁹ representing the package;
- dates, names and numerical results of laboratory tests;
- body height and weight;
- blood pressure readings.

At the time of our first and second studies, each participating practice used to execute a bi-monthly data export from its EMR into the FIRE database using application programming interfaces developed specifically for each of the participating EMR software products. For each practice, EMR data was available from the day it joined the FIRE project. In 2023, the export mechanism was updated to automatically export data in the background on a daily basis, minimizing effort for participating practices. Currently, when a new practice joins the project, a complete data export is performed, going back to the day the EMR software was installed in the practice. These new developments have greatly enhanced the potential of the FIRE database for applications using near real-time data and for long-term retrospective analyses. The third study used data from this updated version of the FIRE database.

On the one hand, the components of the FIRE database make it possible to identify care processes, such as the request for a specific laboratory tests or the prescription of a particular drug, and to evaluate clinical parameters, such as laboratory test results. On the other hand, the various EMR components allow the definition of operationalized criteria for the identification of patients affected by different conditions.⁶⁰ Linking variables with openly available data also enables the generation of additional variables to be considered as determinants:

- Linking the pharmaceutical cost group (PCG) list of the Federal Office of Public Health to medication GTINs allowed more accurate identification of complex conditions such as inflammatory bowel disease or cancer⁶¹;
- Linking the urban-rural typology data of the Swiss Federal Statistical Office with the postal codes of the practice sites allowed for the classification of their urbanity.⁶²

All patients in the FIRE database are anonymized, which exempts the project from ethical approval in accordance with the Federal Act on Research Involving Human Beings⁶³ (BASEC-Nr. Req-2017-00797). Each patient in the database is assigned an identification number that is uniquely linked to the practice in which they are registered. Due to this anonymization, it is not

possible to directly trace patients who have consulted in different practices of the FIRE database. Within each single practice, however, the consultations of all patients can be tracked over time.

1.3.2 Study Designs

For each study, we used a retrospective cohort design and selected the patient cohort according to a common scheme that included the following steps:

1. Definition of an appropriate *inclusion period* (typically several years).
2. Inclusion of patients with at least one consultation during the inclusion period meeting specific *inclusion criteria* in the form of operationalized definitions using the different components of the FIRE database.
3. Among these patients, the exclusion of patients meeting specific *exclusion criteria*, again using operationalized definitions.
4. Definition of a specific *follow-up period*.
5. Identification of a specific *outcome*, which may represent the occurrence of a process or of the achievement of a specific clinical target during the follow-up period.

Table 1 summarizes the specific cohort definitions and outcomes considered in our studies.

1.3.3 Clinical Concepts

In this section, we describe two key clinical concepts that play a critical role in primary care research and that are essential to understanding our studies.

Study	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria	Outcomes
1) Renal function testing in CKD	1) Evidence of predisposing conditions (diabetes, hypertension, or cardiovascular disease) 2) Evidence of CKD	1) Age < 18 years, follow-up of <18 months 2) Age <18 years, CKD stage G5	Achievement of 14 quality indicators, each addressing a sub-population of either of the cohorts 1) or 2)
2) TSH testing in hypothyroidism	First-time detection of elevated TSH levels.	Age <18 years, history of thyroid hormone replacement, overt hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, iodine deficiency, pregnancy, medication with antithyroid effects	Course of follow-up defined as repeat TSH measurement, direct thyroid hormone replacement, or neither
3) Ferritin testing in iron deficiency	At least one primary care consultation	Age <18 years, ferritin testing during the previous year	Ferritin testing*

Table 1: Cohort definitions and designs of the three studies presented. Abbreviations: CKD, chronic kidney disease; GP, general practitioner; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone. * In this study, we considered the use of ferritin testing as an additional outcome along with the incidence of anemic and non-anemic iron deficiency according to different ferritin cut-offs.

Diagnostic cut-offs. In clinical laboratory testing, cut-off values are important tools to help clinicians make informed decisions about diagnosis and treatment.⁶⁴ In simple cases, a diagnostic cut-off can be thought of as a defined threshold of a continuous laboratory parameter such that a reading on one side of the cut-off indicates the absence of a particular condition and thus leads to its exclusion, while a reading on the other side indicates its presence and thus warrants according therapy.⁶⁵ In an effort to ensure consistency and standardization in practice, clinical guidelines often recommend the use of specific cut-off values. For example, the 2012 KDIGO guidelines define reduced kidney function with a cut-off of 60 mL/min/1.73m² for glomerular filtration rate, a measure of kidney function derived from serum creatinine.³¹ The choice of the ideal cut-off for a laboratory parameter is essentially guided by its ability to correctly discriminate between patients who are affected by the underlying condition and those who are not, and between patients for whom appropriate therapy is warranted and those for whom it is not.⁶⁵ Consequently, the guideline definition of a cut-off has the potential to influence treatment decisions for a large number of patients. A recent example is the definition of the European Society of Cardiology guidelines on cardiovascular risk prevention published in 2019,⁶⁶ which defined a substantially lower cholesterol level to warrant cholesterol-lowering

pharmacological intervention compared to previous versions of the guideline.⁶⁷ In fact, this guideline change led to a considerable increase in the proportion of Swiss primary care patients who would qualify for cholesterol-lowering therapy.⁶⁸

Quality indicators. The first study, which addressed renal function testing in the context of CKD, approached the measurement of quality of care through the achievement of quality indicators (QIs). A QI can be generally understood as a quantitative measure of healthcare services that can be used to assess the quality of care.⁶⁹ According to the framework originally proposed by Donabedian⁷⁰ and widely adopted in primary care,⁷¹ meaningful QIs can be classified as addressing structure, process, or outcome. *Structure* QIs involve the structural elements and resources of the setting where care is delivered, including organizational structures, and physical and human resources. In our study, we focused on the use of *process* and *outcome* QIs, which address the occurrence of specific care processes, such as the occurrence of specific laboratory test requests, and the achievement of specific clinical outcomes, respectively.

Based on previous descriptions and validation in the literature, the 2012 KDIGO guidelines, and operationalizability in the FIRE database, we made a selection of 14 process and outcome QIs related to CKD care. Each QI addressed a specific denominator population of patients, such as all patients with established CKD at specific stages, and was considered achieved for all patients in whom a specific process or outcome of care occurred within a specified follow-up time, such as at least one renal function assessment or attainment of a blood pressure target. The patients in a denominator population for whom a QI was achieved formed the corresponding numerator population. Accordingly, we expressed the quality measured by each QI in terms of the corresponding achievement rate, calculated as the ratio of the numerator to the denominator population sizes.

1.3.4 Statistical Approach

In our three studies, we analyzed the determinants and the variation in laboratory testing using a statistical approach involving mixed-effects models (MEMs). MEMs, also called *hierarchical* or *multilevel models* in the literature, provide a useful extension to various classes of regression models.⁷² They allow quantifying the adjusted associations of an outcome variable with multiple determinants while accounting for a hierarchical data structure in which lower-level units of measurement are naturally grouped into upper-level clusters. Because of their dual nature of capturing both associations with determinants and variation between upper-level clusters, MEMs are particularly useful for assessing variation across healthcare providers.^{73,74} In our studies, we used two-level data structures with the lower-level units corresponding to the cohort patients and their treating GPs forming the upper-level clusters. Unlike other estimation approaches to hierarchical data structures such as generalized estimating equations, MEMs make explicit distributional assumptions about the effects associated with the upper-level clusters.⁷⁵ These effects are treated as independent draws from a probability distribution and are therefore called *random effects*, as opposed to the coefficients associated with the determinants, which are treated as model parameters and are therefore referred to as *fixed effects*. Table 2 summarizes the outcome variables and the fixed-effect determinants selected for the MEMs we used in the three studies presented.

In our analyses, we used a simple MEM structure in which the random effects associated with each GP were assumed to be independent realizations of a normally distributed random variable with an unknown variance parameter and mean zero. Each GP-specific random effect was included additively in the corresponding linear predictor, thereby acting as a *random intercept*.

Study and topic	Outcome variable	Determinants (fixed effects)
1) Renal function testing in CKD	Quality indicator achievement: – Yes – No	Patient: sex, age, relevant conditions GP: sex, age Practice: urbanity of location
2) TSH testing in hypothyroidism	Course of follow-up: – Repeat TSH testing – Direct hormone replacement – Neither	Patient: sex, age, TSH level, overt hypothyroidism, primary care utilization GP: sex, age, workload Practice: urbanity of location
3) Ferritin testing in iron deficiency	Ferritin testing: – Yes – No	Patients: sex, age, relevant conditions and clinical factors, history of iron therapy, primary care utilization GP: sex, age, workload Practice: urbanity of location

Table 2: Summary of the regression modeling approaches used in each study. Abbreviations: chronic kidney disease, CKD; GP, general practitioner; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

An important advantage of these MEMs is that the random intercept variance parameter can be estimated from the data along with the fixed effect coefficients, providing direct insight into the variation of the effects associated with the upper-level clusters. This is particularly useful when the MEM under consideration omits determinants measured at the upper-level clusters: The variance of the random intercept distribution is a measure of variation in the outcome variable across the population of upper-level clusters after adjustment for determinants measured at the lower-level units. Specifically, in our case, we used estimates of the random intercept variance derived from models that did not include GP-level determinants, which we called *null models*, to obtain a measure of the variation in laboratory testing across GPs, adjusted for patient determinants. In other words: We used the null models to obtain estimates of the variation in laboratory testing among GPs after controlling for patient characteristics.

For the generalized linear and for survival MEMs that we used in our studies, the scale on which the random intercept variance parameter is estimated is of limited interpretability, as are the fixed-effect coefficient estimates. Analogous to how the fixed-effect coefficient estimates can be converted into more clinically meaningful measures of associations, like adjusted odds ratios and hazard ratios, a variety of intuitive measures of variation derived from the random intercept variance estimate have been described in the literature. In the studies presented, we used the following:

- *Intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC)*, defined as the proportion of variance in the outcome variable that is explained by grouping within the upper-level clusters.⁷⁶ In our first study, we used logistic regression models to analyze QI achievement as a binary outcome variable and used ICCs to express the proportion of variation in each QI achievement rate attributable to the GP. A number between zero and one, values of an ICC near zero and near one indicate a small and large proportion of variation attributable to the GP, respectively.
- *Range odds ratio (ROR)*, derived from the interval odds ratio for mixed-effects logistic regression models.⁷⁷ In our first study, we defined the ROR to be interpretable as the odds ratio for QI achievement for the same given patient between a GP at the 95th percentile and a GP at the 5th percentile of adjusted QI achievement rates. As such, the ROR is a measure of variation that lies on the same scale as the ORs associated with the fixed-effect determinants. It focuses on the spread of patient-adjusted QI achievement rates across GPs, directly comparing the quality delivered by the highest-performing GPs to the quality delivered by the lowest-performing GPs in the sample.
- *Median odds ratio (MOR)* and *median hazard ratio (MHR)*, used for the models of the second and third studies, respectively. These measures express the median relative odds and hazards of success, respectively, for a binary outcome between two randomly selected GPs, comparing the GP with the higher adjusted success rate to the GP with the lower adjusted success rate.^{77,78} Like the ROR, the MOR and MHR lie on the same scale as the corresponding fixed-effect determinant associations in terms of adjusted odds and hazard ratios. Unlike the ROR, they focus on what can be interpreted as an average difference in achieving the respective outcome of interest between any two GPs in the sample. We used the MOR derived from a mixed-effects multinomial logistic regression model⁷⁹ to express variation in the course of action after a finding of elevated TSH levels in the second study, while we used the MHR derived from a mixed-effects Cox proportional hazards model⁸⁰ to express variation in the use of ferritin testing in the third study.

1.4 Summary of Results

In this section, we summarize the main findings of our three studies. Detailed results, in particular measures of determinant association and of variation, can be found in the corresponding full-text articles starting on pages 52, 69, and 77.

1.4.1 First Study

In this study, we evaluated the achievement rates of three QIs related to renal function testing in 47,201 patients (median age 68 years, 48.7% female) affected by at least one major risk factor for CKD (diabetes, hypertension, or cardiovascular disease) and of 11 QIs related to disease management in 14,654 patients (median age 80 years, 57.5% female) with confirmed CKD. QI achievement rates ranged from 18.1% for monitoring urinary albumin to 82.6% for withholding non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug prescriptions in patients with CKD. QIs related to the management of cardiovascular risk factors in CKD were more likely to be achieved in male patients. Diabetes was associated with achievement of QIs related to monitoring of CKD. We observed the greatest variation at the GP level for renal function testing in patients with diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and hypertension.

1.4.2 Second Study

Our second study examined GPs' course of action among 1,591 patients (median age 65 years, 64.4% female) with an initial finding of elevated TSH levels. Of these, 34.3% received repeat TSH testing, 12.4% received direct thyroid hormone replacement, and the remaining 53.3% received neither during 12-month follow-up. Repeat TSH testing was most strongly associated with overt hypothyroidism at inclusion and higher primary care utilization. On the other hand,

direct thyroid hormone replacement was associated with moderate-to-severe TSH elevation at inclusion, overt hypothyroidism at inclusion, female gender, and nonurban practice location. The GP-level variation in terms of MOR was comparable in size to the determinant associations.

1.4.3 Third Study

In our third study, we examined the use of ferritin testing in 255,351 patients (median age 52 years, 52.1% female) presenting in primary care, of whom 28.5% received ferritin testing during the three-year observation period. Ferritin testing was associated with an incident finding of anemia and with a history of iron therapy, and was consistently more common in female patients than in male patients across all age groups, including postmenopausal patients. Female and younger GPs were more likely to request ferritin testing, and the GP-level variation in terms of MHR was comparable to the associations with anemia and iron therapy. At ferritin cut-offs of 15, 30, and 45 ng/mL, the incidence of iron deficiency was 10.9 (95% confidence interval [CI] 10.6 to 11.2), 29.9 (29.4 to 30.4), and 48.3 (47.7 to 48.9) cases per 1,000 patient-years, respectively. Of these iron deficiency cases, 67.8%, 80.0%, and 84.5% represented non-anemic iron deficiency at the 15, 30, and 45 ng/mL cut-offs, respectively.

1.5 Discussion and Interpretation of Results

Our studies are the first to provide a deeper insight into how Swiss GPs use three specific laboratory tests that rank among the most commonly requested analyses in primary care: renal function tests, TSH, and ferritin. Our findings provide an important basis for comparison in an international context and can serve as a reference for developing and evaluating initiatives aimed at the use of laboratory testing in Swiss primary care.

In this section, we provide a broader context for the interpretation of our results. First, we will discuss the most striking patterns in the determinants and the clinical variation of the laboratory tests included. We will then address general findings that point to relevant gaps in their use, and we will discuss how these gaps may arise from issues we identified in the relevant clinical guidelines.

1.5.1 Important Disparities

In our three studies, we found relevant associations between the use of selected laboratory tests and several determinants, highlighting important disparities:

- The quality of renal function testing related to CKD was lower in female patients and in patients without comorbidities in our first study.
- The second study showed potential overtreatment with thyroid hormone in women and in non-urban settings, and a potential underuse of TSH monitoring in younger patients with low primary care utilization following a finding of TSH elevation.
- In the third study, we observed that ferritin testing may be overused in postmenopausal women.

Gender was a recurring determinant, with a particularly striking association in the first study. We observed that male gender was associated with higher quality of renal function testing in both patients with risk factors for CKD and in patients with established CKD. These results reflect findings from the international literature, which indicate a relevant gender gap to the disadvantage of women in cardiovascular risk prevention in primary care.^{81,82}

For our analyses of the second and third studies, we used the number of recorded consultations as a quantifier of primary care utilization, and found a positive association with the use of the corresponding laboratory tests after adjustment for relevant comorbidities. This result can be interpreted in the context of a known correlation between the number of primary care visits and

the use of preventative health measures.⁸³ This relationship may have two consequences: On the one hand, it may imply underutilization of testing in patients who do not see their GP regularly, which we inferred for monitoring of elevated TSH levels in our second study. On the other hand, it may imply a potential for overutilization of low-value testing in patients with regular primary care visits, which is what we suspected in the case of ferritin testing in our third study.

Our analyses also revealed interesting GP characteristics as sources of variation in laboratory testing. The most notable findings came from the third study, where we observed that ferritin testing was more common among female and younger GPs after controlling for workload. However, we note that our use of GP and practice determinants was limited, particularly in our first study, and future analyses conducted with the FIRE database should aim to include more of the professional characteristics to address potential confounding (see section 1.7.1).

1.5.2 Clinical Variation

Clinical variation, also referred to in the literature as *medical practice variation*, has emerged as an important issue in various healthcare settings because it can indicate overuse and underuse,⁹ reduced efficiency, reduced quality, and equity issues.^{84,85} Originally applied to geographic variation in the hospital setting, it has more recently gained attention also as variation at the physician level, especially among GPs.⁸⁴ Historically, the question has been raised as to what clinical variation may be warranted, for instance, because it reflects variation in patient preferences, and what constitutes unwarranted variation that should be avoided.⁸⁶ Sutherland and Levesque⁸⁵ proposed a framework that defines clinical variation as *unwarranted* when it reflects variation in care that does not result from differences in clinical factors that would justify different evidence-based approaches or from differences in patient preferences.

In our studies, we used MEMs to quantify the amount of clinical variation in the use of laboratory testing that was attributable to differences among GPs after adjustment for patient characteristics. In all studies, we considered the observed levels of clinical variation between GPs, expressed in terms of the measures described in section 1.3.4, to be substantial since they were comparable to the observed associations with patient determinants. We note that this variation may not be entirely unwarranted, as it may be due in part to systematic differences in unobserved characteristics of the patient populations seen by different GPs. For example, in our first study, it is conceivable that some GPs take charge of patients with more severe clinical presentations of diabetes requiring closer monitoring of renal function, whereas other GPs refer these patients more frequently to specialized endocrine care.

In the first study, we used the ICC to express the variation in the QI achievement rates, directly comparing the degrees of variation attributable to GPs rather than attributable to the patients. An advantage of the ICC is that it can be reported in an intuitive way using statements such as “*We observed that the GP accounted for 31% of the variation in renal function testing in patients with diabetes*”. However, in the absence of common reference standards, it is generally difficult to judge an ICC as “large” rather than “small”. The only means of comparison remain between different QIs and, where available, with values reported in previous studies.

We assessed factors potentially associated with the observed levels of clinical variation by adjusting for available demographic and professional characteristics of the participating GPs. However, the resulting associations were generally weak compared with the observed associations with patient-level determinants, leaving considerable degrees of still unexplained variation. A notable exception was the third study, where ferritin testing was associated with younger age and female gender of the GP. On the other hand, we note that our inclusion of GP characteristics and of non-clinical patient determinants in our first and second studies can be consid-

ered rudimentary, and that additional associations appear when using variables such as physician workload, practice type, or measures of continuity of care (see the secondary analysis presented in section 1.7.1).

1.5.3 Relevant Gaps and the Role of Clinical Guidelines

Each of the three studies reported a particularly important finding pointing to a relevant gap in the use of the respective laboratory tests:

- The first study suggested that monitoring of urinary albumin may be underused in patients with CKD compared to the guideline recommendation of annual monitoring.³¹
- The second study showed that a large proportion of patients with an incident finding of elevated TSH levels do not receive adequate follow-up in primary care in form of repeat TSH testing.
- In the third study, we observed that the choice of cut-off has a large impact on how often GPs may diagnose iron deficiency, with potentially huge implications for the frequency of subsequent iron therapy.

A common theme in our interpretation of these findings is the context provided by the clinical practice guidelines. Clinical practice guidelines are generally considered to be important tools for helping GPs' decision-making using evidence-based medicine, with the potential to reduce variation and improve quality of care.⁸⁷ On the other hand, their implementation faces several barriers, some of which are due to factors at multiple levels of the healthcare system, and some of which are due to issues related to the guidelines themselves.^{88,89} Here, we discuss such guideline-related issues that need to be considered when interpreting the general findings listed above.

Poor applicability. Guidelines may be based on the results of clinical trials conducted in patients who are not representative of the target population in terms of gender, age, or morbidity. This was particularly evident in the context of our first study, where we observed that the population affected by CKD in primary care tends to be much older than the patients included in relevant clinical trials.⁹⁰ In older patients, concerns about multimorbidity, polypharmacy, and frailty are important components of medical decision making that may present significant barriers to the implementation of guidelines focused on single diseases.⁹¹ Moreover, given the lower life expectancy of elderly patients, individual preferences become increasingly important and often justify overriding evidence-based practice.⁹²

Direct application of the 2012 KDIGO guidelines, on which we based our QI definitions, led to the observation of what can be called an evidence-to-practice gap in terms of worryingly low QI achievement rates.^{93,94} While part of this gap may indeed reflect inappropriate care for some patients, particularly with regard to the variable use of renal function testing in patients with risk factors for CKD, perfect performance on some of the QIs is probably not achievable or not even desirable. The result would be a saturation of QI achievement at an unclear ceiling, falsely suggesting gaps in quality of care (see section 1.6.3). This aspect was particularly important in interpreting our observation that urinary albumin was monitored in only 18% of patients with CKD during 18-month follow-up in contrast to the recommendations for annual monitoring. Again, according to recommendations,³¹ detection of elevated urinary albumin concentrations, or albuminuria, would have required initiation of pharmacological therapy with renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) inhibitors, a class of drugs that slow the progression of CKD by interacting with the pathological mechanisms behind albuminuria.⁹⁵ However, we found in our analyses that 71% of patients with CKD had at least one RAAS inhibitor prescription during 12-month follow-up, presumably because of their main indication as antihypertensive drugs. Thus, urinary albumin monitoring would have remained without a therapeutic consequence for

the majority of patients, and a certain saturation in the achievement of this QI was to be expected.

Inconsistency. Different guidelines for the same condition may provide contradicting recommendations. This was evident in the context of our second and third studies, where review of the literature revealed inconsistencies in recommendations for the use of TSH testing and the interpretation of ferritin concentrations, respectively.^{41-43,52} Although we suggest that guideline inconsistency may be an important source of the observed clinical variation, evaluating this claim is difficult and would require in-depth analyses correlating GPs' views on guidelines with their actions.

Lack of sound evidence. In many cases, the current level of evidence is simply not sufficient for guidelines to provide sound recommendations. While this aspect may contribute directly to clinical variation, it is also related to the previous point, since different medical societies and different expert panels may draw different conclusions from the available inconclusive evidence and thus provide conflicting recommendations, as was evident in the case of ferritin testing.⁵²

In summary, our considerations highlight both the need for harmonization of clinical guidelines and for tailoring them to the primary care setting and its particular needs.

1.6 Strengths and Weaknesses

In this section, we discuss the various strengths and weaknesses of our studies. We address the use of EMRs for research and quality monitoring in primary care, both in general and more specifically in the Swiss context and with regard to the FIRE database.

1.6.1 Electronic Medical Records as a Source of Real-World Data

Data from EMRs belong to the class of real-world data (RWD), which the United States Food and Drugs Agency defines as “*data relating to patient health status and/or the delivery of health care routinely collected from a variety of sources*”.⁹⁶ RWD therefore generally denote clinical information derived under real-world conditions, as opposed to data generated primarily for research purposes under standardized conditions, such as from prospective observational studies or from randomized controlled trials. In addition to EMRs, other sources of RWD traditionally used in health services research include administrative data from health insurance claims and data from surveys. More recently, the wealth of RWD has grown immensely with the advent of new technologies, including advances in biomedical diagnostics, wearable devices, or social media.⁹⁷

Compared to experimental studies, the advantages of using RWD for research arise from their generation in clinical routine: They typically allow for the investigation of large numbers of patients without additional recruitment burden, they tend to be less administratively and financially demanding, and they can often be collected using existing infrastructure.⁹⁸ Most importantly, RWD provide insight into the actual processes of healthcare delivery, allowing both the generation of evidence that can inform policy and the subsequent evaluation of policy responses and impact. Overall, RWD are seen as a fundamental component of a *learning health system*, a model for health systems in which evidence gained from real-world practice informs and improves clinical care in continuous learning cycles.⁹⁹

On the other hand, RWD are usually generated for clinical or administrative purposes, and their use in research is secondary. Observational research conducted with RWD therefore presents difficulties in addition to the usual challenges of observational studies with prespecified measurements, particularly the additional potential for selection, information, and misclassification bias.¹⁰⁰ Initiatives to increase transparency in the reporting of these challenges have led

to the publication of tools such as the RECORD (REporting of studies Conducted using Observational Routinely-collected health Data) statement, which provides a checklist of various items that are recommended to be addressed in published articles.^{101,102} We prepared the manuscripts of our studies according to the guidelines of the RECORD checklist.

1.6.2 Primary Care Research Using Electronic Medical Records

EMRs share most of the general strengths of RWD sources. However, their generation for non-research purposes has several limitations that require careful consideration. Several studies have addressed the potential pitfalls of using EMRs for health services research,^{100,103-105} including in primary care.^{106,107} In this section, we summarize the challenges and potential issues that we believe are most relevant to the interpretation of the studies presented, grouping them into challenges related to representativeness, data quality, and missing data.

Representativeness. To ensure the external validity of results derived from EMR analyses, it is important that the population captured is representative of the population for which the inference is intended. In primary care research, representativeness concerns (at least) two levels: patients and GPs.

For patients, it is important to note that the population represented in EMR visits is often not representative of the general population. Primary care patients tend to have higher morbidity rates than the general population of the same age.¹⁰⁸ This aspect is particularly important when inferring measures of disease occurrence derived from EMRs, such as the incidence of iron deficiency (diagnoses) that we calculated in our third study. Quite surprisingly, in a previous multinational analysis, incidence rates of anemic iron deficiency derived from primary care EMRs were reported as estimates of population incidence rates.¹⁰⁹

At the level of GPs, selection bias may occur due to the participation in research projects involving EMR databases and the use of EMRs rather than paper records in the first place, as discussed below in section 1.6.4.

Data quality. The primary purpose of primary care EMRs is documentation and billing. Accordingly, the quality of the data contained in EMRs can be highly variable, and considerable preprocessing and curation efforts are required to make the data clean for research.¹¹⁰

In the course of our studies, the quality of the laboratory data imported into the FIRE database posed several challenges due to the high variation in the terms used by different practices and laboratories to describe laboratory analyses, a common difficulty in EMR databases.¹¹¹ To address this challenge, our group followed a previously described iterative standardization procedure involving laborious manual review of entries.¹¹² This approach enabled the standardization of more than 13 million laboratory test records in 2019. As the FIRE database continued to grow, the author of this thesis later developed a pipeline to semi-automatically standardize incoming records by matching them to the most similar records already labeled and standardized in the database. Our experience illustrates that considerable human effort is required to ensure quality sufficient for secondary use of EMRs, an aspect that is not always apparent when looking at mere published analysis reports and research manuscripts.

We encountered other relevant data quality issues related to discontinued medication prescriptions that may not be documented by GPs, which are common in EMR data.¹⁰⁴ This imprecision can lead to false positive labels of active prescriptions when considering all prescriptions that are not discontinued at a given time, and thus represents a possible source of misclassification bias. For example, one of the CKD care QIs in the first study assessed whether patients with CKD received prescriptions for RAAS inhibitors. This QI was considered achieved if a patient ever had a record of a non-discontinued prescription at any time during the respective 12-month follow-up period, including non-discontinued prescriptions started before the follow-up period.

We considered the likely overestimation of the QI achievement rate to be acceptable, as it would at most misclassify patients whose GP once had an intention of prescribing a RAAS inhibitor.‡

Missing data. Missing data can arise from a variety of mechanisms and have diverse implications for the interpretation of studies based on EMRs. Based on previous discussions in the literature^{100,104,105,113} and on our experience with the three studies presented, the possible sources of missingness can be approached by considering the care processes involved in the generation of EMR data.

- *Missing data due to variables typically not included in EMRs or not extracted into the EMR database.* Important determinants and outcomes, particularly socioeconomic variables,¹¹⁴ may not have a designated documentation field in EMRs to begin with. Even if retrieved by a GP, the relevant information may only be included in free-text clinical notes. This issue is of particular interest for the FIRE database, where clinical notes are not available and several such characteristics could not be included in our analyses (see section 1.6.4).
- *Missing data because a procedure is not part of the intended care process for a patient.* A laboratory test result, like the result of any diagnostic test, is included in an EMR only when a physician requests its measurement. In other words, the laboratory test results recorded in a primary care EMR database must be interpreted with the understanding that they are observed after the GP has made a decision to order their measurement. For example, the ferritin concentrations that we used in our third study to estimate the incidence of iron deficiency diagnoses were available for a very specific subset of the primary care population: Those patients whose GP decided that ordering a ferritin test was warranted in the first place. Assuming that most ferritin tests result from a specific clinical indication, such as a risk factor for iron deficiency, we expect the distribution of ferritin concentrations observed in the FIRE

‡ Note that in the QI definition of the article, we used the less accurate term “*active prescription*”.

database to differ from the unconditioned distribution in primary care patients. How neglecting this aspect can be misleading is illustrated by comparing our analysis of the use of ferritin testing with previous EMR analyses of the incidence of iron deficiency already mentioned in section 1.6.2. While the authors interpreted the observed associations of clinical characteristics with a diagnosis of anemic iron deficiency as these characteristics causally increasing the risk of developing anemic iron deficiency,^{109,115} we argue that part of these associations simply reflect a higher propensity of certain patient groups to receive ferritin testing, as supported by our findings. More accurately, the identified risk factors therefore represent risk factors for a *diagnosis* of iron deficiency.

- *Missing data due to censoring.* Certain clinical variables may have been assessed outside the setting in which the EMR data were documented, leading to censoring of care events.¹⁰⁰ This is particularly important in primary care, where specialist referrals and hospitalizations may lead to interval censoring. In addition, patients may leave a practice due to events like relocating or death, resulting in right censoring. Conversely, left censoring can occur when patients transfer from another practice, when a practice opens, or when the practice has changed the EMR documentation software without migrating the data from the previous software. Due to censoring, patient cohorts derived from EMRs are typically dynamic, with patients entering and leaving the cohort at different times, and are therefore commonly referred to as *open cohorts*.¹¹⁶ Censoring is highly relevant to the FIRE database and must be considered in the interpretation of most studies, especially since information on hospitalization, referral, practice change, and death is not available (see section 1.6.4).
- *Missing data due to failed entry into the EMR or due to failed import into the EMR database.* This mechanism addresses clinical information that was generated but that got lost somewhere along the chain between the GP and the EMR database due to documentation or technical issues. This type of missing data is considered more of a data quality issue, as it typically does not share the characteristics of the other missing data mechanisms that arise from

the specifics of the care process.¹¹⁰ For example, in our first and second studies, we observed that information on body mass index (BMI) was absent for a large proportion of patients, and it is conceivable that many of the missing observations resulted from measurements that were recorded in the clinical notes rather than in the designated field that we extracted into the database. However, whether such records can be considered missing completely at random is debatable.¹¹³ It is conceivable that GPs are more likely to document abnormal values that require clinical action (e.g., BMI values indicating obesity) and to document values in the presence of conditions where they are particularly relevant (e.g., when other cardiovascular risk factors are present) in the designated EMR fields

1.6.3 Quality Monitoring Using Electronic Medical Records

EMRs are increasingly being used to measure quality and performance in healthcare,^{117,118} making them essential components for quality improvement in learning health systems.^{99,107} The information contained in EMRs can be analyzed in near real time and fed back directly to health system stakeholders, and subsequent quality initiatives can be assessed. However, several issues, mainly regarding data quality, interoperability, and GPs' documentation practices, complicate their use.^{117,119} Another important limitation is that while patient-reported outcome and experience measures have gained importance in the multidimensional assessment of quality of care, they face challenges of interoperability and unclear scalability and are therefore not well implemented in routine care and EMR software.¹²⁰

Monitoring quality in Swiss primary care has recently acquired significant importance in the context of the new obligation for GPs to undertake quality activities (see section 1.1.2).¹⁷ To date, various initiatives and efforts have taken place, notably participation in quality circles,¹²¹ accreditation,¹²² and financial incentive schemes,¹²³ but none of these has ever reached national

coverage.¹⁷ A previous effort to develop a primary care monitoring instrument has been severely limited by a lack of data accessibility and quality.¹²⁴ The new legislation would arguably provide a strong incentive to participate in projects such as the FIRE database, where GPs could minimize any additional burden by delegating quality monitoring to a third party. In fact, we have successfully explored this aspect to recruit GPs for the FIRE project: Since early 2024, in exchange for their participation, GPs have been receiving individualized electronic feedback reports showing achievement rates on a selection of evidence-based QIs. These feedback reports not only improve compliance with new legislation, but also have the potential to directly improve the quality of care delivered to patients.¹²⁵

While EMRs have great potential for quality monitoring in primary care, the lack of a standardized data collection has been a major barrier to effective implementation, an experience shared by several countries.^{17,117,126,127} The adoption of international coding systems, such as LOINC® (Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes) for laboratory tests, or of data exchange standards, such as FHIR® (Fast Healthcare Interoperable Resources),¹²⁸ would greatly facilitate interoperability and increase the usefulness of EMR data for secondary use.¹¹⁷

A common challenge of quality monitoring in primary care is the development and implementation of appropriate evidence-based QIs. Essential features of a high-quality QI are relevance to the health problem under consideration, measurability, reliability, and acceptance by GPs.¹²⁹ The process of developing QIs for primary care is complicated by the fact that guidelines tend to address a single condition at a time, making it difficult to translate to a setting where multimorbidity is prevalent.¹³⁰ In particular, this can lead to ceiling effects in terms of a saturation of QI achievement rates when quality of care cannot be further improved due to limited direct applicability of clinical guidelines. In our first study, this aspect was particularly evident in the interpretation of the QI on urinary albumin monitoring, as outlined in section 1.5.3. Defining QI performance targets is therefore particularly challenging, as is defining

meaningful quality improvement based on increases in QI achievement rates. For example, although we could compare the achievement rates of the 14 QIs we used in our first study with each other and with the international literature, we could hardly tell which of them reflected better or worse GP performance. However, in the absence of absolute goals for QI achievement, benchmarking against best-performing peers has proven to be a promising tool for quality improvement in primary care.^{131,132}

1.6.4 Strengths and Weaknesses of the FIRE Database

The FIRE database is the oldest and largest database of Swiss primary care, covering most cantons in German-speaking Switzerland.⁵⁵ The GPs participating in the FIRE project are broadly representative of the Swiss GP population in terms of demographic and professional characteristics, with a slight overrepresentation of practices in urban areas.¹³³ However, it should be noted that in 2022, almost 20% of Swiss GPs had not yet implemented EMRs in their practices, and it is conceivable that GPs using paper-based records provide different care than GPs using EMRs.^{134,135} In addition, participation in the FIRE project is voluntary, and further selection bias may arise from GPs participating in research projects being more likely to provide higher quality of care.¹³⁶

Although the FIRE database is an important source of data from Swiss primary care, it has several limitations. First, important clinical outcomes such as referrals, hospitalizations, and deaths are not available. This lack of information may lead to censoring and underestimation of the occurrence of certain care processes. Second, the FIRE project only included practices in German-speaking Switzerland at the time of the three studies presented. Differences in the management of hypothyroidism¹³⁷ and in the use of iron therapy⁵⁴ have previously been observed between the different language regions, affecting the generalizability of the results of our second and third studies at the national level. Finally, unstructured components such as free-text

clinical notes, which could contain a large quantity of information including presenting complaints or clinical examination findings, are not available in the FIRE database. In our studies, the identification of patient cohorts, commonly referred to as phenotyping, was limited to the definition of operationalized criteria applied to the various structured EMR components of the FIRE database using what are known in the literature as rule-based methods.^{138,139} Incorporating information contained in clinical notes using more advanced algorithms may increase the sensitivity of identifying certain conditions,¹⁴⁰ meaning that our rule-based methods may have underestimated their occurrence. Since the 2023 updates described in section 1.3.1, the FIRE database has extracted the list of problems and diagnoses from the EMRs of the participating practices, which would presumably be valuable for identifying diseases in the database. However, at the time of our third study, database-wide standardization of relevant problems and diagnoses was not yet available, and we did not include this data source in our analysis.

The lack of information on hard clinical outcomes might be partially addressed by linkage to other data sources. Previous experiences such as in the United Kingdom,¹⁴¹ Canada,¹⁴² or Spain¹⁴³ have shown the potential for enhancing primary care EMR data through linkage to national registries. In Switzerland, health insurance claims data would be a particularly interesting source to link with the FIRE database, as they would provide information on hospitalization and referral. However, their use for longitudinal studies would be limited because a considerable proportion of Swiss residents change switches health insurers each year.¹⁴⁴ While linking EMRs and insurance claims can benefit from the strengths of both datasets, it can also pose several challenges related to data loss.¹⁴⁵ Another interesting source would be the NewIndex dataset, which collects and analyzes billing information of ambulatory care physicians in Switzerland.¹⁴⁶ In addition, the socioeconomic environment could be taken into account by including the Swiss neighborhood index of socioeconomic position for the areas where the FIRE

Characteristic	FIRE database	Health insurance claims	Patient/provider surveys
Recruitment effort	High	Low	High
Size of patient sample	Typically high	Typically high	Comparatively low
Data generation effort	Low (routine data)	Low (routine data)	High
Data preprocessing and curation effort	High	High	Comparatively low
Temporal lag	Near real-time evaluation is possible	Lag due to billing	Lag due to recruitment and data collection
Access to patient-relevant outcome and experience measures	Limited	Limited	Accessible
Access to hard clinical outcomes (hospitalization, death)	Very limited	Accessible	Limited
Access to achievement of clinical targets (laboratory and vital parameters)	Accessible	Limited	Limited
Access to processes of care	Accessible	Accessible	Limited
Access to provider characteristics and experience	Limited	Limited	Accessible

Table 3: Comparison of the FIRE database, of health insurance claims, and of surveys as data sources for assessing the quality of primary care in Switzerland. Judgment based on the discussion of section 1.6.4.

practices are located.¹⁴⁷ Future projects should explore the potential of linking the FIRE database to these data sources to enhance its role for research and quality monitoring in Swiss primary care.

In our experience, the potential of using data from the FIRE project, from health insurance claims, and from surveys that directly capture the experiences of patients¹³ and providers¹³³ holds great but underutilized potential to comprehensively assess the state of primary care in Switzerland within the scope of a learning health system. Table 3 summarizes and compares the strengths and limitations of these data sources, highlighting their complementarity in the Swiss healthcare system.

1.6.5 Evaluating Laboratory Testing Policies Using the FIRE Database

An additional advantage of the FIRE project is that it allows for a quantitative assessment of the impact of policies that target the use of specific health services in primary care. A recent

example in the area of laboratory testing is the amendment to the HIBO that came into effect on July 1, 2022,¹⁴⁸ which restricted the coverage of vitamin D testing by compulsory health insurance to a restricted range of indications.²¹ The volume of vitamin D testing increased substantially between 2006 and 2016, and a health technology assessment conducted in 2020 estimated that up to 30 million Swiss francs could be saved annually by limiting coverage, following the example of other countries.¹⁴⁹ To assess the impact of this change on vitamin D testing in Swiss primary care, we conducted an interrupted time series (ITS) analysis, a quasi-experimental technique commonly used in health policy evaluation.¹⁵⁰ In our case, the basic idea was to compare the temporal trends in vitamin D testing volumes before and after the policy was enacted, interpreting any difference as an estimate of the policy effect. For this analysis, we considered the monthly volume of vitamin D tests per 1,000 consultations registered in the FIRE database from July 2020 to December 2023. We used a segmented linear regression model with two periods: a baseline period (July 2020 to June 2022) before and an intervention period (July 2022 to December 2023) after the change in coverage policy.¹⁵¹ The results of this ITS analysis are summarized in Figure 1, which plots observed vitamin D testing volumes against model predictions in two scenarios: Once in the observed scenario and once in a counterfactual scenario in which the policy change was assumed not to have occurred. For the first month of the policy implementation (July 2022), the model resulted in an estimated reduction of 5.0 vitamin D tests per 1,000 consultations (95% CI 4.1 to 5.8) compared to the 11.3 tests per 1,000 consultations (95% CI 10.6 to 12.1) expected in the counterfactual scenario. The change in coverage policy therefore led to an immediate reduction in vitamin D testing volumes by approximately half. Detailed model specifications and results are provided in the Supplementary Material, Appendix A.

Figure 1: Interrupted time series analysis of vitamin D testing volumes using data from the FIRE database (unpublished analysis). Observed vitamin D testing volumes per 1,000 consultations (crosses) are plotted against the model predictions in the observed scenario (solid blue lines) and in the counterfactual scenario of no policy enactment (dashed blue line). The vertical double arrow indicates the estimated reduction in vitamin D testing volume of 5.0 tests per 1'000 consultations due to the coverage policy change on July 1, 2022. The diagram also shows the fitted seasonal trends in the observed (solid pink lines) and counterfactual (dashed pink line) scenarios. We performed this analysis using the statistical software R, version 4.3.2 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria),¹⁵² and generated the figure using the *ggplot2* package.¹⁵³

The validity of this analysis is somewhat limited by the potential for concurrent initiatives that may have confounded the effect of the billing policy. For instance, the smarter medicine campaign, the Swiss offshoot of the Choosing Wisely campaign,¹⁵⁴ published a set of five recommendations in 2021 aimed at reducing the use of unnecessary and overused procedures in primary care. One recommendation was to avoid routine vitamin D testing in patients without risk factors for vitamin D deficiency.¹⁵⁵ It is conceivable that this recommendation, and the discussions that led to its release by the Swiss Society of General Internal Medicine, contributed to the observed decline in vitamin D testing volumes. More rigorous analysis could go a step further and evaluate the impact of the policy on the diagnostic efficiency of vitamin D testing by looking at the proportion of tests that indicate vitamin D deficiency. In addition, the long-term effects of this policy change are not yet clear, as less than two years had elapsed at the

time of analysis. Nevertheless, this example illustrates how data from the FIRE database can help to assess the impact of policies aimed at the use of laboratory testing in Swiss primary care.

1.7 Methodological Considerations

1.7.1 Choice of Determinants

Comparing the three studies presented, which were all based on the same data source, our choice of determinants seems rather inconsistent (see Table 2). For example, our first study did not take into account the potentially relevant influence of patients' use of primary care services or GP workload, which we considered in the second and third studies. The evaluation and inclusion of determinants has been a learning process, partly hindered by what we perceived to be a lack of standardization in the literature. However, a recent review by McOwiti et al.¹⁵⁶ provides guidance on the determinants that should be considered when evaluating clinical variation in health services research. This article identifies 28 features divided into patient and local context features, with the latter further divided into provider and physician features. Based on our previous experience and on data availability, we have adapted this framework to create a list of determinants that should be considered for inclusion in future studies using the FIRE database. These determinants are summarized in Table 4, where they are divided into the levels of patient, GP, and practice.

In particular, in our first study, we did not use variables that characterize the GP and practice operation style, which may have influenced QI achievement. For this thesis, we therefore conducted a secondary analysis of the QIs concerning the use of renal function testing, including two additional determinants: GP workload in consultations per week and the usual provider of care (UPC) index, a measure of continuity of care.^{157,158} For each patient, we calculated the UPC index by dividing the number of consultations they had with the most frequently seen GP

by their total number of consultations during the follow-up period. A UPC index was therefore equal to one if a patient had consistently consulted a single GP, while it approached zero as the number of GPs consulted during the follow-up period increased. In addition, we included comorbidities in patients with risk factors for CKD and disease stage in patients with established CKD to provide a more consistent representation of clinical patient characteristics. The detailed results of the corresponding regression models are summarized in Appendix Table B1 and Appendix Table B2, along with the results of the original analysis in the published article.

This secondary analysis revealed some interesting associations that provide additional information to the original analysis. In particular, it showed that the presence of comorbidities was strongly associated with the use of renal function testing in patients with risk factors for CKD. In addition, among patients with CKD, stage of disease emerged as a strong determinant, suggesting that disease severity is an influential factor in renal function testing. Note that we did not include a measure of primary care utilization in the form of the number of consultations prior to the start of follow-up as we did in our third study. This was because a large number of patients would have been lost due to lack of historical data prior to the inclusion of the practice in that earlier version of the FIRE database. It is conceivable that the associations of renal function testing with both comorbidities and CKD severity are partly mediated by the frequency of GP visits, and that their inclusion in the model would attenuate the observed associations with comorbidities. The inclusion of professional characteristics also showed interesting effects: QI achievement was less likely in group practices than in solo practices, and was less likely at lower levels of continuity of care.

While these results do not invalidate our original analysis, they do provide us with additional insights that we had not previously considered.

Patient	
Determinant	Remarks
Age	Consider using clinically meaningful categories, such as groups to which different recommendations apply.
Gender	Non-binary gender indicators (“unknown”/“other”) are extremely rare in the FIRE database.
Severity of the condition of interest	Severity of the condition or clinical factor motivating the analysis. Can be expressed in terms of disease stages (such as CKD stages according to KDIGO in our first study) or of levels of clinical parameters (such as the degree of TSH elevation in our second study).
Relevant conditions	May include, but is not limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>Risk factors</i>, i.e., conditions that increase the risk of the condition of interest (such as diabetes or cardiovascular disease in CKD). – <i>Complications</i>, i.e., conditions that often result from the condition of interest (e.g., anemia in iron deficiency). – <i>Comorbidities</i>, i.e., concurrent conditions that may affect the management of the condition of interest (such as diabetes in hypothyroidism).
Relevant clinical findings	Results of laboratory tests or vital signs that may affect management of the condition of interest (such as free thyroid hormone levels in hypothyroidism).
Medication	May include, but is not limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Treatment for the condition of interest (e.g., history of thyroid hormone replacement for hypothyroidism). – Medication that may increase the risk for the condition of interest (e.g., proton-pump inhibitors for iron deficiency).
Primary care utilization	Expressed as the number of consultations in a fixed period strictly preceding the follow-up period.
Continuity of care	Measured by an appropriate metric such as the UPC index (see main text).
General practitioner	
Determinant	Remarks
Age	Can serve as a proxy for experience.
Gender	-
Workload	Expressed in consultation or patient volumes over a given period.
Practice	
Determinant	Remarks
Size	Single or group practice.
Case volume	Expressed in consultation or patient volumes over a given period. Often confounded with practice size and workload of the single GPs.
Urbanity of practice location	Classification as urban/intermediate/rural (or urban/non-urban depending on sample size) according to the Federal Statistical Office. ⁶²
Geographic region	Division by the regions according to the Federal Statistical Office. ¹⁵⁹

Table 4: Determinants to be considered in studies conducted with the FIRE database. This list is an adapted version of the list proposed by McOwiti et al.¹⁵⁶ Abbreviations: CKD, chronic kidney disease; KDIGO, Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone; UPC, usual provider of care.

1.7.2 Multivariate Approaches to Measuring Quality

In our first study, we approached the analysis of the quality in the use of renal function testing by defining a set of QIs and by analyzing each QI independently, fitting a separate regression

model for the achievement of each QI. This approach has been used previously to analyze QI achievement in primary care⁷⁴ and produces results that are rather straightforward to interpret and to communicate to stakeholders. However, we have identified at least two major methodological limitations.

First, the large number of outcomes and of determinants involved naturally raises the issue of multiple comparisons, with the risk of overinterpreting spurious findings, especially when relying solely on statistical significance for reporting results. This challenge can be partially addressed by giving more weight to the actual observed magnitudes of associations rather than to the associated *p*-values, and by considering overarching patterns (such as those discussed in section 1.5.1) rather than focusing on individual determinant-outcome associations when discussing results.

The latter suggestion to consider overarching patterns leads directly to the second challenge we faced: By considering each QI as separate, we ignored possible interrelationships, but it is quite conceivable that common underlying factors (observed and unobserved) may simultaneously influence the achievement of several QIs. For example, while our data suggest that male gender and the presence of comorbidities are positively associated with the quality of CKD care, our individual analyses did not allow us to assess of whether such a *general* association holds. However, quantifying broader relationships would provide additional insight and greatly aid in communicating effectively with stakeholders.

This limitation suggests the need for multivariate approaches to the analysis of quality in primary care to achieve a simultaneous assessment of the associations between given determinants and multiple outcomes. At the same time, in light of the emerging quality initiatives in Swiss primary care, the ability to provide individualized feedback to GPs using concise measures that summarize the quality of care across multiple domains would be particularly appealing. Such *provider profiling* has a long history in the context of hospital care,¹⁶⁰ and

approaches to multivariate profiling using multiple QIs have recently been described.¹⁶¹ However, the literature only describes few attempts to profile physicians across multiple domains of care simultaneously.^{162,163}

1.8 Implications

The studies presented in this thesis revealed important gaps in the use of specific laboratory tests in Swiss primary care, uncovered important determinant associations, and quantified the degree of clinical variation. In this section, we discuss what we consider to be important implications of our findings and discussions for both future research project and policy in Swiss primary care.

1.8.1 Implications for Future Research

First, our results were all derived from a single data source, the FIRE project. The various limitations discussed in section 1.6.4 pose potential threats to their external validity, and future studies, possibly using complementary sources of RWD from Swiss primary care, should validate our observations.

Our attempts to explain the origin of our study results remain speculative. Future research, especially of the qualitative type, that examines the reasons for these differences and the sources of variation, and that takes into account the importance of behavioral aspects of medical decision making, may help to design interventions aimed at improving the quality of laboratory testing in primary care.¹⁶⁴ Our studies could serve as a starting point for the quantitative aspects of such interventions, especially regarding relevant sample sizes and association sizes. In addition, the FIRE project would provide a useful platform for studying such interventions, as it involves a large network of GPs in different regions of Switzerland.

In our studies, we encountered several issues related to clinical guidelines concerning the use of laboratory testing. In general, our discussions underscore the need to tailor clinical guidelines to the specific needs and characteristics of primary care patients.

Finally, the discussion in section 1.7.2 shows that the potential of EMR data for multi-domain quality assessment and physician profiling in primary care has not yet been explored. The FIRE project would provide an ideal data source to explore the possibility of GP profiling using EMRs.

1.8.2 Implications for Policy

As healthcare costs continue to rise in Switzerland, the need to identify specific targets for intervention is critical. Due to its high volume, which has been steadily increasing over the last few years, and its potentially high downstream costs, primary care laboratory testing provides an ideal target for initiatives and measures aimed at improving efficiency. However, a one-size-fits-all approach is unlikely to be sufficient: Our studies suggest that interventions targeting different laboratory tests should take into account the different disparities associated with them, and should address the different gaps associated with the relevant clinical guidelines. In addition, the FIRE project could play a central role in assessing the impact of such policies, as illustrated by the example of the coverage restriction for vitamin D testing in section 1.6.5.

Following our discussion in section 1.6.3, our studies have underscored the potential of EMRs as promising tools for monitoring the quality of services in Swiss primary care. An important feature is their origin in clinical routine, which does not require any specific quality measurement effort on the part of GPs. However, to effectively realize this potential in the future, policies should address the various barriers to data interoperability. This may prove challenging, as the level of digitalization of the Swiss healthcare system lags behind that of other high-income countries,^{165,166} and various digital health initiatives have faced significant challenges due to

regulatory barriers and ineffective collaboration between stakeholders in the highly fragmented healthcare system.^{167,168}

1.9 Conclusions

This thesis examined the use of specific laboratory tests by Swiss GPs using data from a large EMR database. The three studies presented revealed important gaps, disparities, and substantial clinical variation in the tests considered. In particular, we found a potential underuse of urinary albumin monitoring in patients with CKD, a potential underuse of TSH monitoring in patients with elevated TSH levels, and a large effect of ferritin cut-off choice on iron deficiency diagnostic rates. The results of our studies provide important insights that can serve as the starting points for initiatives to improve the quality of laboratory testing in Swiss primary care.

Our findings also revealed relevant shortcomings in several clinical guidelines, namely limited applicability to the primary care setting, inconsistency, and lack of robust evidence, which may explain part of the observed clinical variation. Clinical guidelines need to be better adapted to the setting of primary care, where advanced age and multimorbidity play an important role in medical decision making.

Finally, this thesis underscores the potential of RWD from an EMR database such as the FIRE project to be effectively used to identify areas for improvement, to monitor the quality of services, and to assess the impact of policies in Swiss primary care. However, realizing this potential will not be possible without significant progress in data interoperability in the Swiss healthcare system.

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CHAPTER 2 Quality and Variation of Care for Chronic Kidney
Disease in Swiss General Practice: A Retrospective Database Study

CHAPTER 3 Elevated TSH Levels: A Database Study of General Practitioners' Course of Action

CHAPTER 4 Impact of the Ferritin Cut-Off Choice on the Incidence of Iron Deficiency Diagnoses in Primary Care

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Appendix A: Interrupted Time Series Analysis of Vitamin D Testing Volumes

In section 1.6.5, we describe an interrupted time series analysis of vitamin D testing volumes in Swiss primary care using data from the FIRE database to assess the impact of the health insurance coverage restriction that came into effect on July 1, 2022. As an outcome variable, we considered the monthly vitamin D testing volume y_t expressed as the number of vitamin D tests per 1,000 consultations during the months $t = 1, \dots, 42$. We used an analysis period of 42 months ranging from July 2020 to December 2023 divided into two intervals: A baseline period from July 2020 to June 2022 and an intervention period from July 2022 to December 2023. Our segmented linear regression model used the equation

$$y_t = s_t + \beta_0 + \beta_t \cdot t + [\beta_1 + \beta_{t,1} \cdot (t - t_1)] \cdot \mathbb{I}_{t \geq t_1} + u_t. \quad (1)$$

Here, the parameters β_0 and β_t denote the intercept and time trend (slope), respectively, of the testing volumes during the baseline period. The time t_1 indicates the first month of the intervention periods, and $\mathbb{I}_{t \geq t_1}$ denotes an indicator function assuming the value 1 for $t \geq t_1$, and 0 otherwise. Accordingly, β_1 and $\beta_{t,1}$ denote the level and trend change, respectively, in the intervention period relative to the baseline period.¹ To account for seasonality, we included a linear combination of cosine and sine functions of periods 6, 12, and 18 months in the term s_t with unknown coefficients $\gamma_1, \delta_1, \gamma_2, \delta_2, \gamma_3, \delta_3$:

$$s_t = \gamma_1 \cos\left(\frac{\pi t}{3}\right) + \delta_1 \sin\left(\frac{\pi t}{3}\right) + \gamma_2 \cos\left(\frac{\pi t}{6}\right) + \delta_2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi t}{6}\right) \\ + \gamma_3 \cos\left(\frac{\pi t}{9}\right) + \delta_3 \sin\left(\frac{\pi t}{9}\right). \quad (2)$$

The unobserved effects u_t were assumed to be realizations of independent draws of Gaussian distributions with zero mean and unknown variance, potentially varying with t .

The interpretation of the model parameters becomes particularly clear when considering a counterfactual scenario in which the policy change did not occur. According to (1), the expected value of vitamin D testing volumes at the beginning of the intervention period in the observed scenario where the intervention took place equals $s_{t_1} + \beta_0 + \beta_t \cdot t_1 + \beta_1$, while the expected vitamin D testing volumes in the counterfactual amount to $s_{t_1} + \beta_0 + \beta_t \cdot t_1$. Hence, the coefficient estimate for β_1 , which represents the difference in expected vitamin D testing volumes at t_1 between the two scenarios, can be interpreted as the immediate effect of the coverage policy on vitamin D testing volumes.

We performed the analysis using the statistical software R (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria²) and estimated the model parameters using generalized least squares as implemented in the *nlme* package,³ yielding the results in Appendix Table A1. To account for heteroscedasticity of the u_t , we used a power variance structure as specified by the `varPower()` function.⁴ The residual plot in Appendix Figure A1 and the residual autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation plots in Appendix Figure A2 did not indicate any substantial heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, or nonstationarity, and we refrained from using more complex model structures (such as autoregression) for this illustrative example.

Coefficient	Coefficient estimate (standard error)	95% confidence interval	p-value
β_0	13.339 (0.334)	12.683 to 13.994	<0.001
β_t	-0.102 (0.023)	-0.147 to -0.057	<0.001
$\beta_{t,1}$	0.029 (0.032)	-0.034 to 0.092	0.373
β_1	-4.967 (0.428)	-5.806 to -4.128	<0.001
γ_1	-0.179 (0.100)	-0.374 to 0.017	0.083
δ_1	-0.330 (0.102)	-0.530 to -0.130	0.003
γ_2	0.337 (0.115)	0.113 to 0.562	0.006
δ_2	-0.118 (0.122)	-0.357 to 0.120	0.337
γ_3	-0.105 (0.149)	-0.396 to 0.186	0.485
δ_3	0.942 (0.140)	0.667 to 1.217	<0.001

Appendix Table A1: Coefficient estimates for the interrupted time series analysis of the change in coverage policy for vitamin D testing. Coefficients are labeled according to (1) and The coefficient β_1 denotes the immediate effect of the policy change.

Appendix Figure A1: Residual plot for the interrupted time series analysis of the change in coverage policy for vitamin D testing.

Appendix Figure A2: Residual autocorrelation (top) and partial autocorrelation (bottom) plots for or the interrupted time series analysis of the change in coverage policy for vitamin D testing (dashed blue lines: 95% confidence intervals).

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Appendix B: Secondary Analysis of Quality Indicator Achievement

Variable	QI 1		QI 2		QI 3	
	Original	Secondary	Original	Secondary	Original	Secondary
Intercept	1.91 (1.23 to 2.99)	7.32 (2.89 to 18.56)	1.37 (0.97 to 1.93)	2.85 (1.37 to 5.92)	1.71 (0.99 to 2.96)	4.73 (1.61 to 13.87)
Male patient	1.14 (1.04 to 1.25)	1.25 (1.08 to 1.45)	1.11 (1.05 to 1.16)	1.01 (0.94 to 1.10)	1.05 (0.96 to 1.14)	1.08 (0.95 to 1.23)
Patient age (reference: <40 years)						
40-59 years	2.26 (1.84 to 2.78)	1.60 (1.17 to 2.20)	1.65 (1.45 to 1.88)	1.61 (1.34 to 1.95)	1.59 (1.08 to 2.33)	1.03 (0.58 to 1.83)
60-79 years	3.62 (2.96 to 4.43)	2.45 (1.78 to 3.38)	2.71 (2.39 to 3.08)	2.37 (1.97 to 2.85)	2.42 (1.66 to 3.54)	1.38 (0.79 to 2.43)
≥80 years	4.67 (3.70 to 5.89)	2.70 (1.87 to 3.90)	3.54 (3.09 to 4.06)	2.92 (2.37 to 3.58)	2.85 (1.94 to 4.19)	1.62 (0.91 to 2.87)
Diabetes	-	-	-	1.80 (1.63 to 1.98)	-	1.74 (1.50 to 2.02)
Hypertension	-	1.19 (0.99 to 1.43)	-	-	-	1.55 (1.31 to 1.83)
Established cardiovascular disease	-	1.03 (0.87 to 1.23)	-	1.20 (1.09 to 1.31)	-	-
Continuity of care (reference: single practice)						
Group practice, UPC = 1	-	0.29 (0.14 to 0.60)	-	0.44 (0.24 to 0.80)	-	0.42 (0.20 to 0.91)
Group practice, UPC ≥ 0.5	-	0.26 (0.12 to 0.55)	-	0.46 (0.25 to 0.85)	-	0.44 (0.20 to 0.97)
Group practice, UPC < 0.5	-	0.10 (0.03 to 0.26)	-	0.29 (0.15 to 0.58)	-	0.08 (0.03 to 0.21)
Male GP	0.67 (0.47 to 0.94)	1.04 (0.58 to 1.87)	0.74 (0.57 to 0.97)	0.77 (0.50 to 1.19)	0.80 (0.57 to 1.11)	0.99 (0.54 to 1.80)
GP age (reference: <45 years)						
45-59 years	0.90 (0.64 to 1.27)	0.71 (0.40 to 1.23)	0.89 (0.68 to 1.17)	0.87 (0.57 to 1.34)	0.83 (0.59 to 1.16)	0.74 (0.42 to 1.31)
≥60 years	0.73 (0.43 to 1.22)	0.58 (0.26 to 1.28)	0.84 (0.55 to 1.27)	0.97 (0.53 to 1.76)	0.82 (0.49 to 1.38)	0.72 (0.32 to 1.61)
GP workload (reference: <100 consultations/week)						
100-199 consultations/week	-	0.48 (0.27 to 0.86)	-	0.56 (0.36 to 0.88)	-	0.34 (0.19 to 0.60)
≥200 consultations/week	-	1.23 (0.42 to 3.60)	-	1.11 (0.48 to 2.54)	-	1.51 (0.52 to 4.36)
Urban practice location	1.12 (0.78 to 1.61)	0.94 (0.53 to 1.67)	1.07 (0.80 to 1.44)	0.99 (0.63 to 1.56)	1.11 (0.78 to 1.60)	0.90 (0.50 to 1.63)

Appendix Table B1: Comparison of the results of the original and of the secondary analyses for the quality indicators (QIs) 1-3 of our first study using additional determinants. These QIs assess the presence of at least one request for renal function testing (as either serum creatinine or urinary albumin) in primary care patients aged 18 years or older with diabetes (QI 1), hypertension (QI2), or cardiovascular disease (QI 3) during 18-month follow-up. Abbreviations: GP, general practitioner; UPC, usual provider of care index.

Variable	QI 4		QI 5	
	Original	Secondary	Original	Secondary
Intercept	1.95 (1.52–2.49)	1.23 (0.82 to 1.85)	0.17 (0.10–0.30)	0.25 (0.15 to 0.42)
Male patient	1.10 (1.01–1.19)	1.14 (1.04 to 1.24)	1.51 (1.29–1.77)	1.44 (1.24 to 1.67)
Patient age (reference: <65 years)				
65-79 years	1.15 (0.99–1.34)	0.91 (0.77 to 1.09)	0.62 (0.49–0.79)	0.77 (0.62 to 0.97)
≥80 years	1.07 (0.92–1.24)	0.76 (0.64 to 0.91)	0.22 (0.17–0.28)	0.30 (0.23 to 0.38)
Diabetes	1.58 (1.44–1.75)	1.61 (1.44 to 1.79)	3.76 (3.17–4.45)	3.84 (3.28 to 4.50)
Hypertension	1.30 (1.19–1.42)	1.34 (1.22 to 1.48)	1.17 (0.98–1.39)	1.13 (0.96 to 1.33)
Established cardiovascular disease	1.37 (1.25–1.51)	1.41 (1.27 to 1.57)	0.90 (0.74–1.10)	0.94 (0.78 to 1.13)
CKD stage (reference: G1-2)*				
G3a	-	2.19 (1.80 to 2.67)	-	0.26 (0.20 to 0.33)
G3b	-	2.99 (2.42 to 3.68)	-	0.29 (0.22 to 0.37)
G4	-	3.22 (2.50 to 4.15)	-	0.42 (0.31 to 0.59)
Unknown	-	0.69 (0.45 to 1.04)	-	1.07 (0.68 to 1.68)
Continuity of care (reference: single practice)				
Group practice, UPC = 1	-	0.72 (0.55 to 0.95)	-	0.79 (0.54 to 1.15)
Group practice, UPC ≥ 0.5	-	0.75 (0.57 to 1.00)	-	1.43 (0.99 to 2.06)
Group practice, UPC < 0.5	-	0.48 (0.26 to 0.87)	-	0.57 (0.32 to 1.02)
Male GP	0.84 (0.71–0.99)	0.88 (0.71 to 1.09)	0.86 (0.59–1.26)	0.86 (0.59 to 1.25)
GP age (reference: <45 years)				
45-59 years	0.80 (0.68–0.95)	0.79 (0.64 to 0.97)	1.69 (1.13–2.53)	1.60 (0.87 to 2.96)
≥60 years	0.79 (0.62–1.01)	0.67 (0.50 to 0.90)	0.82 (0.45–1.51)	0.99 (0.67 to 1.45)
GP workload (reference: <100 consultations/week)				
100-199 consultations/week	-	0.88 (0.72 to 1.07)	-	0.25 (0.15 to 0.42)
≥200 consultations/week	-	0.79 (0.57 to 1.10)	-	1.44 (1.24 to 1.67)
Urban practice location	0.94 (0.80–1.12)	0.94 (0.76 to 1.16)	0.80 (0.53–1.22)	0.77 (0.62 to 0.97)

Appendix Table B2: Comparison of the results of the original and of the secondary analyses for the quality indicators (QIs) 4-5 of our first study using additional determinants. These QIs assess the presence of at least one serum creatinine (QI 4) or urinary albumin (QI 5) testing request in patients aged 18 years or older with established chronic kidney disease (CKD) during 18-month follow-up. Abbreviations: GP, general practitioner; UPC, usual provider of care index. * G stages according to estimated glomerular filtration levels as defined in the 2012 KDIGO guidelines.⁵

Appendix C: Confirmation of Author Contributions

First study: Jäger L, Rosemann T, Burgstaller JM, Senn O, Markun S. *Quality and Variation of Care for Chronic Kidney Disease in Swiss General Practice: A Retrospective Database Study*. PLOS ONE, 2022. 17(8): p. e0272662.

Second study: Jäger L, Burgstaller JM, Zechmann S, Senn O, Rosemann T, Markun S. *Elevated TSH Levels: A Database Study of General Practitioners' Course of Action*. Endocr Pract. 2024;30(3):187-193.

Third study: Jäger L, Rachamin Y, Senn O, Burgstaller JM, Rosemann T, Markun S, The FIRE Study Group. *Impact of the Ferritin Cutoff Choice on the Incidence of Iron Deficiency Diagnoses in Primary Care*. [Submitted for publication]. 2024.

Author Contributions

	1 st study	2 nd study	3 rd study
Conceptualization	U, SM	U, SZ, SM	U, YR, SM
Data curation	U	U	U
Formal analysis	U	U	U
Funding acquisition	TR	TR	TR, JMB
Investigation	U	U	U
Methodology	U, SM	U, SM	U, YR, SM
Project administration	TR, JMB	TR, JMB	TR, JMB
Resources	TR, JMB, OS	TR, JMB, OS	TR, JMB, OS
Software	U	U	U
Supervision	SM	SM	SM
Validation	U	U	U
Visualization	U	U	U
Writing – original draft	U	U	U
Writing – review & editing	All authors	All authors	All authors

Signatures

X

 Jakob M Burgstaller

X

 Oliver Senn

X

 Stefan Markun

X

 Stefan Zechmann

X

 Thomas Rosemann

X

 Yael Rachamin

Appendix D: Disclosure Regarding the Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools

Throughout this thesis, the author used the online tool *DeepL Write* (DeepL SE, Cologne, Germany; <https://www.deepl.com/write>) for English-language editing to correct orthography and grammar and to increase readability. No other artificial intelligence-based technology was used to assist in the writing of the text, the literature review, or the analyses included in this thesis. The author takes full responsibility for the content of this thesis.